

Symptoms exhibited by RTBV strains on rice cultivars FK135 (a) and TN1. (b) Left to right: healthy plants (check) and plants infected with strains Ic, G1, G2, and L.

genes (one for TN1 and another for FK135) are involved in RTBV symptom expression. RTBV strains could be used for comparative studies on the mechanisms of pathogenicity of the virus. ■

Inheritance of resistance to rice blast disease in some japonicas

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Rice blast (BI) disease (*Magnaporthe grisea* [Hebert] Barr) is a major constraint to rice production in China. Crosses of the susceptible variety, Nongfu 6 (NF6), and five resistant varieties, Xianghu 84 (XU84, derived from C81-45//Ce 21/Xianghu 14), Xianghu 25 (XU25, derived from Aijing 23/Xianghu 14//Ce 21/Aijing 23), Xiushui 04 (XS04, derived from

Table 1. F₂ segregation of S/R^a crosses with resistance to the 3 rice BI races.^b

Race	Cross	Reaction (no.)							χ^2	
		Parents		F ₁		F ₂			3:1	15:1
		R	S	R	S	R	M	S		
ZB ₁₃	NF6/XH84	9	0	9	0	296	1	19	0.1949	0.0034
	NF6/XU25	26	0	10	0	305	4	16		0.7633
	NF6/XS04	13	0	11	0	528	2	33		0.0863
	NF6/XS11	9	0	11	0	213	0	76		0.3127
	NF6/XS24	9	0	11	0	442	3	26		
	NF6	0	10							
ZC ₁₅	NF6/XH84	9	0	9	0	261	2	16	0.0048	0.0538
	NF6/XU25	21	0	10	0	279	3	16		0.2586
	NF6/XS04	18	0	11	0	415	0	26		0.0437
	NF6/XS11	8	0	11	0	204	4	68		0.1815
	NF6/XS24	11	0	11	0	449	0	27		
	NF6	0	10							
ZE ₃	NF6/XH84	9	0	9	0	284	2	17	2.3050	0.1164
	NF6/XU25	17	0	10	0	275	0	18		0.0021
	NF6/XS04	18	0	11	0	453	6	26		0.5115
	NF6/XS11	9	0	11	0	242	7	67		0.0382
	NF6/XS24	15	0	11	0	321	1	20		
	NF6	0	10							

^aR = resistant, M = moderately resistant, and S = susceptible. ^b5% significance level, $\chi^2 = 3.84$.

Table 2. F₂ segregation of R/R crosses with resistance to the 3 rice BI races.^a

Race	Cross	Reaction (no.)					χ^2	
		F ₁		F ₂			63:1	255:1
		R	S	R	M	S		
ZB ₁₃	XU84/XU25	10	0	523	0	2	0.0001	0.0988
	XU84/XS04	17	0	531	0	2		0.0842
	XU84/XS11	12	0	469	1	8		0.0040
	XU84/XS24	18	0	612	0	3		0.0501
	XU25/XS04	16	0	735	0	2		
	XU25/XS11	18	0	927	0	0		
	XU25/XS24	15	0	461	0	0		
	XS04/XS11	11	0	461	0	7		0.0049
	XS04/XS24	10	0	569	0	2		0.0328
	XS11/XS24	13	0	562	1	8		0.0203
ZC ₁₅	XU84/XU25	10	0	666	1	2	0.4750	0.0049
	XU84/XS04	17	0	528	0	2		0.0895
	XU84/XS11	12	0	392	1	4		
	XU84/XS24	18	0	563	0	0		
	XU25/XS04	16	0	756	0	0		
	XU25/XS11	18	0	684	0	0		
	XU25/XS24	15	0	507	0	0		
	XS04/XS11	11	0	512	0	0		
	XS04/XS24	10	0	518	0	0		
	XS11/XS24	13	0	489	0	0		
ZE ₃	XU84/XU25	10	0	391	0	0	0.0161	
	XU84/XS04	17	0	548	0	0		0.0026
	XU84/XS11	12	0	481	0	8		0.1029
	XU84/XS24	18	0	518	0	2		
	XU25/XS04	16	0	848	0	0		
	XU25/XS11	18	0	907	0	13		0.0541
	XU25/XS24	15	0	604	0	0		
	XS04/XS11	11	0	880	0	14		
	XS04/XS24	10	0	584	1	1		0.2731
	XS11/XS24	13	0	518	0	0		

^a5% significance level, $\chi^2 = 3.84$.

Ce 21/Xianghu 14), Xiushui 24 (XS24 derived from (Ce 21/Xianghu 14)²/Xianghu 25), and Xiushui 11 (XS11, derived from CE 21²/Xianghu 25) were used to study the inheritance of resistance to three BI races, ZB₁₃, ZC₁₅, and ZE₁, during 1991-93.

The seeds of parents, F₁, and F₂ were sown in 60- × 30- × 7-cm plastic trays, one cross/tray. Seedlings were inoculated at the 4-leaf stage by spraying an aqueous spore suspension of 5 × 10⁴

conidia/ml. Disease reactions were scored about 10 d after inoculation.

The results indicated that two dominant genes controlled resistance to three BI races in XU84, XU25, XS04, and XS24, and only one dominant gene controlled resistance in XS11 (Table 1). Testing allelism of resistant parents indicated that some resistance genes were allelic, depending on BI races used (Table 2). ■

Senawee, Sufaida 172, ADR52, and ARC5752 were highly resistant to mealybug. N22, Rening, Oha, Sathra 265, and Katuyhar Dhan were moderately resistant (see table). ■

Pest resistance—insects

Resistance to rice mealybug in whitebacked planthopper-resistant rice varieties

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Resistance to rice mealybug (*Brevennis rehi*) was evaluated in rice varieties possessing diverse genes for resistance to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) (*Sogatella furcifera*) using the seedbox screening test. Five replications were made. Pregerminated rice seeds were

sown in rows in a 30- × 25- × 6-cm seedbox.

At 7 d after sowing, each seedling was infested with 5-6 first-instar nymphs (crawlers). When about 90% of the susceptible check, TN1, had died, plant damage was rated on a 0-9 scale as 0 = no damage, 1 = slight damage, 3 = first and second leaves of most plants partially browned, 5 = pronounced browning and stunting or about half of the plants wilted or dead, 7 = more than half of the plants wilted or dead and remaining plants severely stunted and covered with a mealy coating, and 9 = all plants dead.

Rice mealybug damage ratings on rice varieties resistant to WBPH.^a Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Gene for resistance to WBPH	Origin	Damage rating ^b
Boegi Boera	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Indonesia	5.8 b
N22	<i>Wbph 1</i>	India	3.4 cd
Muskhan 41	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Pakistan	2.2 def
Siam Garden	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Peru	3.0 cde
Rening	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Indonesia	4.2 c
Senawee	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Sri Lanka	1.0 g
Oha	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Nepal	3.8 c
Sathra 265	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Pakistan	3.8 c
Sufalda 172	<i>Wbph 1</i>	Pakistan	1.0 g
ADR52	<i>Wbph 3</i>	India	1.0 fg
Podiwi A8	<i>Wbph 4</i>	Sri Lanka	1.4 fg
N'diang Marie	<i>Wbph 5</i>	Senegal	1.4 fg
WC1240	<i>Wbph 1 + 1</i> recessive	India	3.0 cde
Katuyhar Dhan	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 2</i>	Nepal	3.4 cd
ARC5752	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 2</i>	India	1.0 fg
Colombo	<i>Wbph 2 + 1</i> recessive	India	3.0 cde
Chala Anaser	<i>Wbph 1 + Wbph 3</i>	Nepal	1.8 efg
TN1 (susceptible check)			9.0 a

^aMean of five replications. ^bIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Resistance to thrips in traditional rice varieties

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We evaluated 100 traditional rice varieties for resistance to *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) under field conditions at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, Coimbatore, during Oct 1993.

Pregerminated seeds were direct seeded in three 1-m rows. The resistant check, Ptb 21, and the susceptible check, TN1, were sown between every 10 test varieties. Varieties were exposed to natural thrip infestation. Damage was scored 30 d after sowing (DAS) using the 1-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

S. biformis population and plant damage ratings on traditional rice varieties under field conditions. Coimbatore, India, October 1993.^a

Variety	Population	Damage rating ^b
Co 2	9.0	cde 1.0 c
Co 4	8.2	def 1.0 c
Co 25	8.8	cde 1.4 c
Co 26	8.0	def 1.4 c
Co 27	7.8	def 1.0 c
Co 28	7.4	def 1.0 c
Co 30	7.4	def 1.0 c
ADT10	8.0	def 1.4 c
ADT25	9.8	cd 1.0 c
Ptb12	11.8	c 1.4 c
Ptb21 (resistant check)	6.0	f 1.0 c
PLR1	6.8	def 1.0 c
Thodavalan	9.0	cde 1.0 c
Kandagasalai	6.0	f 1.0 c
Valanchannel	8.8	cde 1.4 c
Chethuvalli	7.8	def 1.4 c
Karuvali	6.6	ef 1.0 c
Kodagan	8.6	cdef 1.0 c
Vali	22.8 b	3.0 b
TN1 (susceptible check)	74.8 a	9.0 a

^aMean of five replications. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05) by DMRT. ^bScored using 1-9 scale in SES.